

Precision and accuracy: The relative standard deviation in the determination of nickel (14.85 mg) by the given method was $\pm 0.4\%$ in 20 determinations.

Determination of nickel in the presence of other ions: The procedure was the same as in the absence of foreign ions. The interference in some cases was removed by working at low pH to prevent the precipitation of corresponding hydroxides. Interference due to Fe(III) was removed by adding potassium tartrate. By suitable adjustment of pH, a number of cations and anions could be tolerated e.g., Ca(II) and Ba(II) (about 20 times), Al(III), Cd(II), Pb(II), Zn(II), Hg(II), Mn(II), Co(II), (about 2 to 3 times), Mg(II) (about 10 times), large amount of tartrate, citrate, chloride and nitrate could be tolerated at pH 5.0 to 5.5.

From the solution containing both copper and nickel, copper was first precipitated and estimated at pH 3.0 as reported⁹ earlier and from the filtrate nickel was precipitated by addition of more reagent and adjustment of pH 5.0 to 5.5 as indicated above. The results are reproducible with an error $\pm 0.4\%$ for amounts of Ni(II) ranging from 2.97 to 15.0 mg. The reagent is readily prepared and less expensive.

Composition of the complex: The nickel complex was analysed to determine the composition. (Found: Ni, 13.68; N, 6.62, Calc: Ni, 14.16; N, 6.75%). The molecular weight determined cryoscopically using camphor as solvent showed the complex to be monomeric, i.e., the complex could be represented by ML_2 . The 1:2 composition of the complex was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation, potentiometric and conductometric studies. The formula of the complex may therefore be represented as $Ni(C_{10}H_{14}O_2N)_2$. The complex can be extracted in benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride.

Examination of the IR spectrum of the reagent showed strong bands at 3400 cm^{-1} (ν OH chelated), 2980 cm^{-1} (ν OH of $=N-OH$), 1640 cm^{-1} (ν C=N), 980 cm^{-1} (ν N-O) and 790 cm^{-1} (1,2,4 trisubstituted benzene). Examination of the IR spectrum of the chelate shows that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal because the band at 2980 cm^{-1} due to hydroxy group of the oximino moiety appears more or less at the same position in both the ligand and the complex and 3400 cm^{-1} peak of the chelated OH disappears in the complex. In the chelate the band at 1640 cm^{-1} disappears and a stronger band appears at 1610 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to C=N shifting down field, due to complexation.

The UV and visible spectra were mapped using solution of this complex in chloroform and peaks at 300 nm, 375 nm and 600 nm were obtained. The magnetic susceptibility of this chelate showed that it is diamagnetic in character.

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Effect of UV Light on Aqueous Solution of Tartaric Acid in the Presence of Nitrogen under Heterogeneous Conditions

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SYNTHESIS of specific life forming molecules is at present being investigated under conditions believed to have existed in the pre-biological era of earth. The problem of abiotic synthesis of such compounds has been discussed by a number of workers i. e., Oparin, Haldane, Miller, Ponnampereuma and others¹⁻⁹. They have emphasised that the molecules that are fundamental today were fundamental at the time of abiogenesis of living matter. It has been suggested that in the ancient abiotic periods of earth, diverse types of organic compounds would have been formed by various methods which would not have required any kind of living or vital forces. Tartaric acid one of such compounds under nitrogen atmosphere was irradiated by ultraviolet light with a view to see the formation of life forming molecules.

It is well known that tartaric acid in aqueous solution decomposes rapidly when exposed to UV light giving a variety of products¹⁰⁻¹². However, the action of UV light on aqueous solution of tartaric acid under nitrogen atmosphere has not yet been studied. Therefore, it was considered of interest and the effect of UV light on aqueous solutions of tartaric acid in the

presence of sensitizers and nitrogen atmosphere has been studied and the results have been presented in this communication.

Materials and Methods :

Extra pure tartaric acid (0.1%, B. D. H./E. M) solution was prepared in redistilled water and 250 ml of this solution was taken in each of four sterilized quartz glass vessels. Extra pure organic and inorganic sensitizers were then added to these vessels under aseptic conditions. The purity of sensitizers was tested prior to their addition to the experimental solutions. These flasks were connected with each other by sterilized glass connecting tubes and kept under UV irradiation chamber. The inlet of the gas passing tubes was connected with nitrogen gas generating unit. Nitrogen gas was prepared freshly (by using extra pure $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{NaNO}_2$) and passed through dilute H_2SO_4 and water in order to wash out ammonia. The pure gas was then bubbled through the sterilized solutions in quartz flasks kept in UV irradiation chamber. The solutions were first saturated with N_2 for an hour by passing a continuous stream of gas and then exposed to ultraviolet source upto 25 hr. Continuous stream of N_2 was passed through out the course of the experiment. The exposed solutions were drawn out aseptically, concentrated in a rotatory vacuum evaporator, examined for any microbial contamination by usual techniques¹³⁻¹⁴ and then the portions of the concentrates were analysed chromatographically employing Whatman No. 1 paper ($18.5 \times 22.5''$, 24 hr at $20 \pm 2^\circ$), Sillica Gel G or Cellulose layer (MN 300) as stationary phase and n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 1, v/v ; 9 : 1 : 1, v/v) or butanol : acetic acid : pyridine : water (15 : 3 : 12 : 10, v/v) as solvent systems. The authentic amino acids were run concurrently alongside of the concentrate as reference standards. The chromatogram was first dried in air, then at 60° , examined under UV black light lamp for marking fluorescent spots and eluted with water for further characterization. For locating and characterizing the resulting products ninhydrin (0.1 g/100 ml acetone), alloxan (0.2 g/100 ml acetone), isatin (0.2 g/100 ml acetone), and Folin's reagent (0.02% 1-2 naphthaquinone-4-sulphonate in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate) were used as colour producing reagents.

Dinitrophenyl derivatives of provisionally identified amino acids were prepared and characterized by comparing their properties with authentic DNP amino acids as reported in our earlier communications⁸⁻⁹. Thus the photolytic products were characterized by their comparison with the authentic DNP amino acids, R_f values, m.p. mixed m.p. of DNP derivatives coincidence chromatography, noting their characteristic fluorescence under UV black light lamp (3650 \AA) and also by specific chemical and spectral methods.

Results and Discussion

When an aqueous solution of tartaric acid in the presence of potassium dihydrogen phosphate under N_2

atmosphere was exposed to UV light for 1 hr, appearance of a product II in poor amounts was noticed. When exposure time was increased to 5 hr, two new products III and IV were detected on the chromatogram. On prolonging the irradiation period upto 25 hr products I, V and VI appeared on the papergram in addition to the products observed for 5 hr exposure to UV light. However, the concentration of all the products increased on increasing the irradiation period upto 25 hr. When sodium molybdate, titanium dioxide, acenaphthene were used as sensitizers in aqueous solutions of tartaric acid under nitrogen atmosphere for the same period of irradiation (25 hr), no new ninhydrin positive compound could be detected except those observed when aqueous solution of tartaric acid was exposed to UV light in the presence of potassium dihydrogen phosphate. Out of these six products formed, four products were tentatively characterized as glycine (II), α -alanine (III), α -amino-n-butyric acid (V) and valine (VI). Results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF UV IRRADIATION (25 hr) OF TARTARIC ACID IN THE PRESENCE OF N_2 GAS UNDER HETEROGENEOUS CONDITIONS

Reaction Mixture	Products of photochemical synthesis					
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Tr W N_2 KP	+	Gly	Ala	+	Buty	Val
Tr W N_2 NaM	+	Gly	Ala	+	Buty	Val
Tr W N_2 TiO ₂	+	Gly	Ala	+	Buty	Val
Tr W N_2 Ac	+	Gly	Ala	+	Buty	Val
R_f^*	.06	0.12	0.16	0.22	0.32	0.42
Colour with ninhydrin	VR	RV	V	Y	V	V
Alloxan	R	P	RP	—	RP	R
Isatin	—	BrP	DB	—	VB	RP
Folin's Reagent	—	GP	GB	—	GB	BGr
O-Phthalaldehyde	—	GR	—	—	—	—
DNP. Dvts.						
R_f^{**}	—	0.34	0.48	—	0.49	0.58
m.p.	—	201°C	170°C	—	—	130°C
Fluorescence in UV black light lamp	W	BW	W	W	BV	BV

—, not detected ; +, positive test or poor yield ; W, water or white ; Y, yellow ; B, Blue ; R, red ; V, violet ; G, grayish ; Gr, green ; P, purple, D, dark ; KP, potassium dihydrogen phosphate ; NaM, sodium molybdate ; Ac, acenaphthene ; Tr, tartaric acid ; Gly, glycine ; Ala, alanine ; Buty, α -amino-n-butyric acid ; Val, valine ; *, in n-butanol:acetic acid:water (4:1:1, V/V) at 20-12°C, **, in tert amyl alcohol-3% ammonia (1:1, V/V).

Product III resembled glycine in its resolution factor (0.12), coincidence chromatography, m.p of DNP derivative (201°) and colour reaction with naphthaquinone reagent (greenish purple), ninhydrin (red violet), isatin (brownish purple) and alloxan (purple). The identity of this compound as glycine was further ascertained by the appearance of green colour with o-phthalaldehyde which turned purple on adding urea (.2%) to the reaction mixture and brown on exposure to UV light of 365 m μ . It on ninhydrin mediated oxidative degradation, afforded, like authentic glycine, formaldehyde, which was detected with cromotropic acid. Absorption spectra of both products II and authentic glycine showed λ_{max} 2100.

Product III when deaminated with nitrous acid (10% HCl+5% NaNO₂) in micro capillary tube and the liberated product on oxidation with acid permanganate gave acetaldehyde which gave blue colour with Rimini reagent. One ml of this reagent (10% dimethyl amino-benzaldehyde in HCl) was diluted to four volumes of acetone before use. Being acidic in nature it destroyed the colour produced by ninhydrin and a purple yellow colour was appeared exactly similar to that of authentic α -alanine.

Product V was identified as α -amino-n-butyric acid by its R_f value (0.37), co-chromatography and reaction with ninhydrin (violet) alloxan (purple), Folin's reagent (greenish blue) and isatin (violet blue). Its DNP derivative (m.p. 132°) resembled with that of authentic α -amino-n-butyric acid. Product VI was characterized as valine by the identity of its R_f (0.40), co-chromatography and characteristic colours with ninhydrin (violet), isatin (reddish purple), alloxan (red) and Folin's reagent (bluish green) with that of valine. This product showed bluish white fluorescence under UV black light lamp. Other properties of the products are recorded in Table 1.

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Influence of Some Complexing Agents on the Reactivity of Indian Rock Phosphates

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FROM a study of the action of some complexing agents on the reactivity of various Indian rock phosphates it appears that the complex forming capacity of the agent with the ingredients of the rock phosphates plays a decisive role in releasing more phosphate in solution. The amount of phosphate passing into the solution increases with the lapse of time to a marked extent which may be due to the hydrolysis and subsequent complex formation. The efficiency of phosphate release by complexing agents used varies in the order of EDTA > Oxine > Cupferron > Dimethyl glyoxime. A number of contradictory reports have recently appeared in literature regarding the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates^{1,2}. According to Vaid³ almost all the rich reserves of Rajasthan rock phosphates except only 8% of the Jhamar Kotra rock are less reactive and can not be used without concentration. Hajra and Chakravarti⁴ advocated the use of some chelating agents for increasing the release of phosphates from insoluble iron and aluminium phosphate minerals. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to study the effect of some complexing agents on the reactivity of various rock phosphates so as to ascertain the economic utility of these phosphates available in abundance in different parts of India.

Experimental

Rock phosphates from Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar obtained through Geological Survey of India were powdered, sieved through a 100 mesh sieve (B.S.S.) and analysed in accordance with the procedure described by Washington⁵.